

GENDER AND INCLUSION: A FOCUS ON MUSLIM WOMEN IN INDIA

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"Gender equality must be a lived reality."

- Michelle Bachelet

This series of research papers emerges out of a discussion that we had with the late Prof Madhava Menon who tirelessly worked for diversity in the work force and against discrimination of all kinds. It was his inspiration that drove us towards the first volume on Gender and Inclusion. This one is the second in the series that we have planned at a biannual frequency, and focuses on Muslim women, a minority within a minority. With the emergence of an appeasement narrative has come up another on the relative deprivation of Muslim women. The agenda has been, in many ways, driven by the Prime Minister himself, with his push towards passing an Act on the Muslim divorce proceedings and in giving criminalising what is essentially a civil wrong.

This narrative therefore triggered several debates, and the various concerns regarding Muslim women has emerged. Do they only serve as baby producers, are they harassed and harangued within their houses that they cannot emerge out of? Do they suffer on the hands of a patriarchal mindset that does not allow them to go to school and later prevents them from seeking employment? In a gendered atmosphere where Indian women continue to do poorly, does the Muslim women face double the hurdles her other compatriots tackle? This volume looks at a few of these questions and tries to develop an understanding of the multiple problems that get highlighted.

Muslims make up around 14.5 percent of India's population. Some two hundred million Muslims live in India- by far the largest minority group in a predominantly Hindu country. India is also the country with the world's third largest number of Muslims after Indonesia and Pakistan. However, there are clear indications that the Muslim minority in India is deprived, discriminated and marginalised. Within the Muslim community, women face even bigger challenges and find it difficult to improve their standards of living. This issue focuses on the situation facing Muslim women in India and gets together some of our best academics to look into this issue. At a time when the parliament has passed a bill recommending reservation for women in the Parliament, that will in all probability take another ten years to get implemented, the debate of women rights becomes central to the development challenges the country faces.

The Indian Constitution guarantees liberty, equality, equity, justice and fraternity; the seventy-year-old document enshrines egalitarian principles which include social equality, non-discrimination and right to freedom of religion (Articles 25-28). In 1976, the word “secular” was added to the preamble. Although with the 42nd Amendment of the Constitution of India (1976), the Preamble asserted that India is a secular country, the Supreme Court of India in the S.R Bommali v. Union of India established the fact that India was secular since its formation of the republic itself. However, **the Constitution does not explicitly require the separation of religion and government.**

A cursory glance over Indians' life ratings is suggestive of regional disparity - the rating is low especially in rural East compared to South. The differences in living standards and poverty continue to prevail in some regions despite the growth of the economy. The reasons could be cultural and linguistic barriers impacting their internal migration and one of the explanations offered by the economists is the poor governance in the less developed states which hinders the investment from private sector to establish their businesses and take advantage of the cheap labour (Crabtree, 2018).

The Muslims in India & the unfinished agenda

Indian Muslims are an integral part of the nation, and their history is part of Indian history. Ideally the development process should accrue to all across faith and culture; remove economic and social barriers, if any. But the Sachar Committee Report (2006) and other empirical studies have established the fact that the Muslim minority is the most deprived in terms of level of living and human development. The Sachar report was the first ever attempt to analyse the socioeconomic development of Muslims community which was based on a large-scale empirical data. The report is a watershed moment in the history of post-independence India. It identified many inequities for Muslim society in India. Issues faced by Muslims are multifaceted; in addition to lower markers on development indices, the community simultaneously face problems relating to security, identity, and equity, and *“the interplay of these dimensions is at the core of the socioeconomic and political processes that the community is exposed to on daily basis”* (Basant & Shariff, 2010). The post Sachar report that came a decade later pointed out to the fact that while the rising tide had lifted the lot of Indian Muslims too, the gap between the majority and the minority has widened. Several reports (Sachar, 2006; Shariff & Basant, 2010; Kundu Report, 2015; Maizland, 2022), provide evidence to show how Muslims in India experience discrimination in employment, education and housing; encounter barriers in achieving political power and wealth; lack access to or have limited health care and basic services.

The post-Sachar, the Kundu committee (2015) evaluated the condition of Minorities in India and found that the Muslim minority has not undergone any cognizable improvement. The report is based on the data drawn from NSSO as there was no government data available to evaluate the comparative situation of minority communities. The report further highlights the fact that the recommendations of Sachar report have not been implemented properly; it observes that there is huge gap between the strategies suggested and their implementation.

Seventy-five years since Independence, Muslims have failed to achieve equality in several front and true 'development' remains a mirage. *Indian history of Muslims depicts how they have been visibly invisible in the processes of democratization* (Jahan, 2016). The Gallup survey provides a window to gauge the perceptions and prospects of people; the surveys in India points to a rather alarming trend during the past few years. The 2021 survey indicates that both the majority and minority communities have been struggling economically, "but their economic pain has not been evenly distributed, as Muslim Indians are far more pessimistic about their future prospects than Hindus" (Reinhart, 2022). Both Hindus and Muslims perceive that their standards of living took a sharp drop between 2018-2019, *as the Indian economy entered a deep slow down*. There is a perceptible jump in percentage in both among Hindus and Muslims, but among Muslims it is relatively higher- from 25% in 2018 to 45% in the year 2019 (ibid). But the current 12% gap between the two communities' perceptions that their living standards are worsening is the largest in Gallup's trend. The same trend is observed in the affordability of food in the face of rising inflation and that they are finding it very difficult to get by on their present household incomes.

Despite constitutional protection, the targeted exclusionary practices and victimization continues to haunt the community, which has further intensified in recent years. The struggles and disproportionate economic 'pain' the largest minority in India is facing, may result in their further marginalization which could likely have serious repercussions on the country as a whole (Ning, 2022).

Marginalization is a process which pushes certain communities/individuals to the periphery of social space that constraints their life choices at the political space, social negotiation, and economic bargaining...*and is inextricably linked with inequality within the marginalized communities* (Jahan, 2016). Muslims in communally sensitive areas generally suffer from insecurity, resulting in ghettoization and restricted mobility especially for women. Gradually, *the creation of 'otherness' plays a determining role in the process of ghettoization of Muslims and quest for identity* (Yasmeen Jahan, ibid). Identity markers result in suspicion and discrimination by people and

institutions, leading to a sense of alienation. The overall impact is reflected in the inability of Muslims to exploit the economic opportunities. Globalization & liberalization processes appear to have affected adversely on Muslim women's occupation in particular and Muslims in general than others. Women are found working in large numbers in home-based industries where their bargaining power is very low. To establish their own units, they lack credit facility. *"Muslim concentrated areas are designated as 'red zones' where credit flow is virtually non-existent"* (Basant & Shariff, *ibid*).

Arnold Rose defines (1972) 'Minority' as a group of people differentiated from others in the same society by race, nationality, religion or language, who both think of themselves as a differentiated group and are thought of by others as a differentiated group with negative connotations. Further, they relatively lack power and hence are subjected to certain exclusion, discrimination and other differential treatments. In 1983, the Gopal Singh Committee, instituted by the government, stated clearly that Muslims are a backward community in India because of their exceptionally poor socio-economic status, particularly among women. Muslim women remained invisible when we talk about the formal and professional sectors of the economy. With such a picture of marginalization and invisibility of women in the public sector in India, it is a foreseeable inevitability that Muslim women are further headed towards the bottom (Malik, 2023). A recent study in Uttar Pradesh- a seminal work in many ways-as this study estimates poverty, wealth inequality and financial inclusion, for the first time, at the sub-caste level in both Hindus and Muslims, observes that *"exclusion from formal financial services forces Dalits to depend primarily on informal financial sources for borrowing... (pg;1227) The biggest policy takeaway from this study is the vulnerable Dalit Muslims who are equally or more deprived than Hindu Dalits but missing from affirmative actions of the government policies (pg.1254)* (Tiwari et al, 2021). *"Muslims are the most deprived minority in the labour market"* (Kundu Report, 2015). *Social exclusion theorists like Sukhdeo Thorat, Amartya Sen, Arjan de haan, Hilary Silver etc., argue that social hierarchical structure, persistent inequality, various forms of discrimination; poverty and unemployment are the leading causes of marginalization.* (Jahan, *ibid*).

Why does Gender Equality matter?

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are a set of 17 goals adopted by the UN to transform our world by ending poverty and inequality and ensuring that all people enjoy health, justice and prosperity. The holistic aim is to 'leave nobody behind' through focus on equality of opportunity and equality of outcomes, inclusive socioeconomic development, no discrimination before law etc.; *"That defining principle of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development is a shared promise by every country to work together to secure*

the rights and well-being of everyone on a healthy, thriving planet. But halfway to 2030, that promise is in peril" (Secretary General UN, 2023). The Report by the UN Secretary General (2023) is not very promising- to say the least. The report is a reflection of the persistent gap between the promises the countries made and their implementation efforts (if at all there were/are any!). In the area of gender equality too, it is a matter of great concern to observe that the countries are not 'on track' to achieve this, as is anticipated by 2030! Goal-by goal "*gender inequalities remain pervasive in each and every dimension*" (UN Women, 2018). The world is far from nearing the targets in all its 18 indicators (except one close to target). If the 'progress' moves at this rate, "*it will take up to 286 years to close gaps in legal protection and remove discriminatory laws, 140 years for women to be represented equally in positions of power and leadership in the workplace, and 47 years to achieve equal representation in national parliaments*" (UN Report *ibid*). The recent global crises have only further exacerbated the existing gender inequalities such as unequal access to health care, education, economic opportunities, the report further observes. Gender based discrimination is a universal phenomenon, is deeply rooted and it "*threatens to undermine the transformative potential of the 2030 Agenda in real and measurable ways*" (UN Women, 2018). The situation in other areas (Goals) and targets set is not promising either. With the initial favourable trend in few areas like extreme poverty, child mortality rate -there was a fall; also, some targets in gender equality were seen showing positive results; some inroads were also made against few dreadful diseases, but it was later realized that whatever progress made was slow in pace and was fragile. Most notable observation is "*the trend is universal, but it is abundantly clear that the developing countries and the world's poorest and most vulnerable people are bearing the brunt*" (UN report, *ibid*).

The UN Secretary General's Report on progress towards SDGs is clearly a pointer to the widening gap between the developed and developing countries; also, it observes in no unequivocal terms that the poorest and the most vulnerable are bearing the brunt! Various surveys, reports and studies have proved beyond doubt that the Muslims in India are the most backward- the Sachar study has placed them below the Scheduled caste and scheduled tribes; the Kundu committee report (2015) found not much improvement in their situation. The faith- based majoritarian rule has only added fuel to the fire. Going by the global surveys (BBC report, 2023), there has been a surge in divisive politics. Addressing the issue of current state of Muslim minority, its exclusion and the false narrative of inclusion, a report observes, "*In India's majoritarian politics, the very idea of the minority is divisive in nature*" (Basak, 2023). The cascading effect of 'identity politics within a divisive system is taking its toll on over all status of Muslims. In a society which is

divided on many fronts, the gender divide is the most prominent one and has its debilitating effect on women and on their overall growth and development.

Gender equality and empowerment of girls and women is an explicit goal under 2030 and is also a driver of sustainable development in all its dimensions. Several Global Gender Gap reports observe that, talent is very essential for competitiveness and to search the best talent, everyone should have equal opportunity *“when women and girls are not integrated ... the global community loses out on skills, ideas and perspectives that are critical for addressing global challenges and harnessing new opportunities”* (Deshpande, 2021).

The Scenario

An attempt has been made in this volume to ascertain the strength, struggles and vulnerabilities the Muslim women face in creating their own spaces in public sector and identify the undercurrents. The volume tries to search for an answer to the question- Is our development inclusive? Is the narrative of inclusion that has been floated today, fair to the minority communities, especially Muslims? What accentuates their marginality? Further, an attempt has also been made to gauge India's efforts towards its commitment to women's cause, along with international agencies such as the UN, and whether India has made an effort to walk the talk!

The special issue **“Gender & Inclusion- with a focus on Muslim Women”** contains ten articles, most of them are based on empirical studies. The articles explore various dimensions of Muslim women's lives. In doing so the authors have tried to provide a deeper understanding of the growing divides between communities and the marginalization of minorities. The authors further made an attempt to discuss thread-bare the various centrifugal forces which are responsible for the exclusion of Muslim minority women from the mainstream, and which are keeping them away from growth and development. The analyses reiterate the need to reassess the false narrative of development and draw recommendations which are of policy implication for their inclusion.

It is an established fact that discrimination, inequity, oppression and exclusion are interwoven. To create equity in any area, it is critical to foster a culture of equity. The institutionalized incapacity Muslim women suffer owing to illiteracy or lower level of literacy, limited exposure to mass media and access to money and restricted mobility, results in limited areas of competence and control. Women's empowerment is impacted by limited autonomy in many areas that has a strong bearing on development.

Propounding that equality is antithesis of inequality, in E.P. Royappa v. State of T.N(53 AIR 1974 SC 555) the Supreme Court held “Equality is a dynamic concept with many aspects and dimensions, and it cannot be cribbed, cabined and confined with traditional and doctrinaire limits. From a positivistic point of view, equality is antithetic to arbitrariness. In fact, equality and arbitrariness are sworn enemies; one belongs to the rule of law in a republic while the other, to the whim and caprice of absolute monarch. Where an act is arbitrary, it is implicit in it that it is unequal both according to political logic and constitutional law and is, therefore violative to Article 14” (Chakroborthy, 2018. Pg. 11).

Under the false narrative of “equality” the present ruling govt is trying to implement UCC by replacing the existing personal laws across various religious faiths against spirit of the Constitution. Personal laws are faith based and are the principles of life, adhering to them is an essential part of a believer. Articles 14-24 under fundamental rights advocate individual rights to equality and freedom while articles 25-30 talk about protection of religious freedom and education and culture rights of minorities. It is from the latter that religious groups derive the right to be governed by ‘personal laws. UN Declaration of Human Rights (1948) gives the liberty to all to practice the religion of their choice, and India is a signatory to the convention; even Convention on the Elimination of all Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW) was signed in 1993 with a reservation that section 16 which deals with uniform personal laws, was not attested. This is because it was felt that a compulsory uniform civil code cannot be enforced. The present government seems to have gone back on this position (Agnes, 2016). While talking about UCC and why gender justice is hard to achieve with a uniform law, she opines that “it is better to reform personal laws and ensure that laws of all communities are gender-just rather than enacting a law which is uniformly applicable to everyone across religions. *The aim should be uniformity of rights, not a uniform law. Because she feels, all personal laws are gender unjust, but they are not gender unjust in the same way....* and that reforms from within and changes through judicial intervention are far more relevant and meaningful for women from minority communities. The lesson that must be drawn is that uniform law by itself would not ensure gender justice. And diverse personal laws can be reformed to be gender just (Agnes, 2016).

The Centre for Development Policy and Practice, Hyderabad invited people from diverse background, legal luminaries, journalists, academia, industrialists and activists to deliberate on Uniform Civil Code (UCC) and to explore its advantages, challenges, and socioeconomic and cultural implications. The discussion emphasised that there is a strong need to preserve the cultural diversity of India and the importance of inclusive dialogues in shaping policies that cater to the needs of India's religiously and culturally diverse population. Moumita & Khan's paper “**Uniform Civil Code in India,**

Balancing Unity and Diversity” is largely based on the outcome of this discussion. Referring to tribal communities and the Northeast, *the critics argue that implementing a common civil code would erode these communities' special privileges, granting them a measure of autonomy to follow their customary laws.* The resistance seems to have made a dent in the thinking of central govt to reevaluate its policy and exempt the tribal communities from the purview of UCC. *The shifts indicate a recognition of the necessity to address the sensitivities and demands of the diverse communities in the region.* The paper also talks of the inclusion of LGBTQ+ and the live in relationship and UCC and challenges there off.

It is observed that there is a need to reform Indian Muslim Personal Law, and that the Muslim community should critically evaluate the evolution of their religious laws and consider reforms. The paper cites Prof. Faizan Mustafa, an Indian academic and legal scholar, who emphasised that Muslim law is predominantly shaped through interpretation and the extraction of principles from the Sunnah (teachings and practices of Prophet Muhammad). The authors observe “quoting Allama Iqbal, Prof. Mustafa suggested revisiting the Quranic verses, emphasising the importance of distinguishing between moral and legal commandments for continuous updating and independent legal reasoning within Muslim law and that the Western legal system primarily revolves around the formulation of laws, which are subsequently subject to interpretation by courts. Conversely, the Islamic legal framework operates on a distinct paradigm where the primary focus lies in interpreting the sources before the actual formation of laws. In this context, interpretation assumes precedence over the legislative process”. It is felt that there is a strong need to observe caution in handling UCC. Uniform Civil Code requires seeking common ground that upholds principles of justice, equality, and inclusivity while still honouring the diverse religious landscape of India opines the authors as a way forward.

In India, with the change of political leadership at the centre, the sanctity of religion-based family law of Muslims has been contested leading to the development of a new sociopolitical discourse which is influenced and shaped by the basic feminist ideals of equal rights for women (Rasheed & Sharma, 2021). The discourse is based on the premise that the laws are unjust to Muslim women and hence need immediate intervention from secular state to safeguard and protect their rights. It created a huge debate-both in support and against it. the Islamic scholars, Muslim women, feminists, and political leaders-all vie with each other in justifying their views on the issue.

Four chapters in this volume address issues confronting Muslim women-the protection of Muslim women's rights related to marriage, marital disputes, divorce, maintenance and the role of Ulema & the judiciary, the pitfalls therein

and the best ways possible to resolve these contentious issues. Further, there is a quest; whether the debate and the political (so called) reforms have been in anyway beneficial to Muslim women? The scholarly arguments put forth by the authors are diverse and each deal with highly important aspects within the ambit of MPL and identify the loopholes in present system and provide a way forward for trans-formative change to protect the rights of Muslim women.

Afra Saleem raises concerns about the skewed nature of justice delivery system in her article “**Muslim Women's Voices in the Adjudication of Marital Disputes in India**”. She is of the opinion that at present the adjudication of marital disputes in our country is dominated by men, both the government recognized Qazi system or non- state fora such as Darul Qazas, popularly known as Sharia Courts. Afra also deals with the issue of gender equality and its importance in procuring justice to the oppressed Muslim women. The paper eloquently discusses the various forms of termination of a Muslim marriage available in Sharia, various Acts and powers of Qazies, the difficulties Muslim women face while annulling their marriage through DMMA and its consequences in India. The author highlights the various complications and issues related to various methods of divorce and comes up with an idea to deal with marital disputes, by setting up of a more robust legal framework using methods of alternative dispute resolution and setting up of a government recognized Muslim mediation, Arbitration and Reconciliation Centre (MARC) given the existing realities on the ground with a specified gender ratio linked to family court system which she feels will certainly be a game changing move. It also argues for a more robust legal framework using methods of alternative dispute resolution and the setting up of a government recognized Arbitration Centre through which the full scope of a female Qazi’s powers may be realized.

Anubhav Bishen’s article “**Family Law reforms in relation to Muslim women in India, A comprehensive debate on Entry points and Thematic areas**”. The article brings forth three entry points and five thematic areas to signify the various intersecting ideas that have come to affect the debate on Muslim family law reforms in India. Anubhav’s insightful arguments provides a chronological order to the debates focusing on Muslim women rights in a secular, democratic, multiculturalist country and highlights how the oppressive, religious and sociocultural practices laid ground for an extensive theoretical debate between multiculturalists and feminists. In doing so the author extensively draws a historical perspective on law, religion and patriarchy. Have these debates, in any way, helped in improving the condition of Muslim women or they have only *allowed to deflect the attention to multiple peripheral issues that the cause of Muslim women has been lost in the process?* The paper also made an attempt to bring forth some normative and theoretical ideas to that the author felt should be brought to the mainstream by

pushing the irrelevant aside so to move the debate in the right direction. In doing so the author underscores the citizenship rights of Muslim women in India. He feels there is a need to postulate a framework of citizenship rights of Muslim women which *should be placed above the group or community rights that usually blind the policy makers.*

Formal education plays a pivotal role in a woman's life- it provides her voice, liberty, decision making power, personal autonomy, provides her chance to exercise choice, and freedom from power structures like patriarchy- most importantly, provides her an agency. Muslim women in India, as is proved by several reports are least represented in formal education, they are at the bottom of the education hierarchy among all communities. The status of women needs to be viewed in the context of their access to knowledge, economic resources and political power as well as the degree of autonomy they have in decision-making and making personal choices at crucial points in their life cycle (UN, 1975). Status of women has to be viewed in the context of their access to knowledge, economic resources, and political power in addition to their autonomy to participate in the process of decision- making (UNDP, 2004; Acharya et al, 2010).

Vaishali's article deals with **“Gendered Struggle for Muslim Girls, Exploring Challenges Towards Accessing Higher Education”**, the study was conducted to understand the construction and reconstruction of aspirations of Muslim adolescent girls, who are at the verge of completing their school education. This paper explores the transitional phase from school to life after school for 12 Muslim girls living in a Muslim dominated habitation of Northeast Delhi. The paper reflects on the larger discussion on the spatial and socio-economic factors contributing to the poor representation of Muslim girls in higher education. The study observed that class followed by gender, as two most influential factors affecting girls' aspirations and the decisions made for the girls. It is the contestations over exercising “choice”, remain a class as well as gendered struggle within household and neighbourhood spaces for Muslim girls in the study. It is further followed by discussion on the contemporary state's thrust on offering vocational courses to “empower” Muslim women, whose families have already been engaged in small-scale skilled businesses for ages; thus, further encouraging the poor community members, and the Muslim girls to opt for learning some skill rather than going for higher education. The study finds reproduction of class and gender for these Muslim girls when it comes to adhering to the state's projected idea of empowerment. Entry into a university, especially for a regular graduate programme, remained an elusive goal for most of the girls interviewed. The paper thus finally concludes by stating that university still remains an exclusionary space for many girls belonging to the largest religious minority in terms of access to higher education.

Vaishali's empirical study strongly points towards the lack of agency among the Muslim girls. Despite their aspirations to pursue higher education, they are unable to do so because of their vulnerability to patriarchy. It is important that the Govt, instead of allocating gendered area of vocation, could think of alternative skill training to bring them out of the vicious cycle of class and gender. Lack of formal education deprive economic independence to girls and women. The study solicits indigenous recommendations on how the barriers that keep Muslim women away from bank best be overcome. Literacy and livelihood, the study observes, are seen as the most prominent signposts that Muslim women need to get past on their way to bank.

Dominant discourses on Muslim women have revolved around their marginal locations in community as well as in society; "*marginality is not only a lived experience, but it also has a metaphoric dimension. The state of marginality relates not only to the poor socioeconomic status of Muslim women but the politics of representation of their identities*" (Sur, 2014). "*Marginality is generally used to describe and analyse socio-cultural, political and economic spheres, where disadvantaged people struggle to gain access (societal and spatial) to resources and full participation in social life*" (Gurung & Kollmair, 2007. 8). It is closely related to the vulnerability of both people and environment as "*it victimizes location and communities that are characterized by one or more factors of vulnerability*" (Sommers et al. 1999, 13). The important components in vulnerability to marginality are gender, age and disability; indeed, gender inequity is a constant challenge that affects women's employment and income potential (Mehta, 1995) and their ability to overcome limitation.

Sanghmitra Acharya's article delves on "**Contextualising marginality and women-How does it affect their health and well-being**". The paper traces the evolution of the concept of marginality in the context of women, it also examines the dyad of knowledge producers and knowledge consumers in the context of women in general; and women's health, and women from the margins in particular. The author uses the term "Dalit" in its literal context and therefore include all women marginalized on the basis of their social identity-caste, ethnicity, and religion. To understand women's health, she feels, it is important to re-examine the theoretical underpinnings, particularly of the women's health movement. The author used the NHFS 4 data for analysis. The extensively well researched paper brilliantly explores the various dimensions of marginality and explains how ethnicity, caste and religion intersect with other axes in carving out marginalization among women by using gender lens. Those in margins, observes Sanghmitra, engage in arduous labour with lesser remuneration as compared to those in the core, thus impacting on their differential access to resources which enhance their health and well-being. *Marginality comes in many forms and impacts women in*

different way-often accentuating their vulnerabilities, says the author. The paper, in doing so, examines the shift from the women as an entity to their heterogeneity. The paper further asserts that, the differentials across gender and between women of different hues socially, economically and regionally, is evidenced from National family and Health surveys and other data. Therefore, it is imperative to recognize women's marginality in general as compared to men; and among women, across axes of caste, ethnicity and religion. Only then can the policy outcome take the desired shape.

Paulo Freire's book "Pedagogy of the Oppressed" (1970) argues that education is not a neutral process. Education either functions as an instrument which is used to facilitate the integration of the younger generation into the logic of the present system and bring about conformity to it, or it becomes "the practice of freedom," the means by which men and women deal critically and creatively with reality and discover how to participate in the transformation of their world. Education plays a pivotal role in bringing in the social, economic and cultural change. Knowledge and skills are essential ingredients to sustain economic progress and a requirement for inclusive growth.

Religious and cultural factors often play a partisan role when it comes to women in family. The patriarchal forces found to maintain and reinforce social exclusion of women and girls especially in Muslim community (Udin, 2012). Muslim women's backwardness in the spheres of education, economy and political participation reflect their subordination and subjugation in the family which results in their social exclusion (Brenner, 1996). Soma **Wadhwa's** empirical study from rural North India "**Barriers to Financial Inclusion for Muslim Women, A Case Study from India**" tries to bring forth yet another important aspect of inclusion i.e., the participation of Muslim women in banking. Despite the government's financial inclusion drive, the study observes among its women research subjects, Muslims are the weakest at accessing and availing banking services. Wadhwa makes an interesting observation that despite a series of educational programs and reforms in India, communities that are variously vulnerable and marginalized due to the issues they face in integrating with mainstream society continue to remain backward on the literacy front. She makes a reference of NHFS-4 of 2015-16 while observing that the extremely high level of illiteracy appears to be playing out in Muslim women's inability and ineptitude with banking as the NHFS-4 shows that Muslim women's access to money and awareness, and use of micro-credit, is poorer than for Indian women in total. According to the author, beyond establishing the correlation, however, deeper investigations reveal that illiteracy is only one among the many impediments between Muslim women and banks. In fact, a complex amalgam of religious-socioeconomic barriers, including illiteracy, keeps them from banking. This

article draws from the study to construct a narrative around detection of these barriers.

Two papers in this special issue deal with the issue of Muslim women's struggles and the barriers in achieving higher education and financial inclusion, respectively. Vaishali and Wadhwa both show some commonalities in their results of empirical studies they have undertaken, though in different parts of India. Wadhwa also provides robust evidence, as does Vaishali, that the Muslim community realizes that a multitude of hurdles confronts its women on their way to financial inclusion and that these barriers stem from restrictions on women imposed by socio-religious practices, including curbing their access to basic literacy and education. Wadhwa's in depth account of three villages provides an absolute picture of a gendering process in making of a Muslim woman. Restrictions on their movements, obedience to elder (read males), prevalence of *purdha* system all points towards the lack of autonomy. Girls are sent to Madarsa and withdrawn upon reaching puberty, regular schools are avoided for girls as this can spoil their character. Girls' movements outside home and neighbourhood are not considered safe. Going to the bank, owning an account is beyond imagination. Male member's bank account is treated as family's account.

For the overall development of a society, it is imperative that both men and women have their share in all development indices. Formal education, skill development and regular employment are the essential parameters to push the community towards empowerment. "There is no tool for development more effective than the education of girls and empowerment of women" (Annan, 2004). India discriminatory report (2022) points out that the periodic labour force survey (PLFS) data for the year 2019-20 demonstrates a significant difference between Muslims and non-Muslim population of 15 years plus in regular employment, with latter showing a 7.8 percentage points higher. Decomposition analysis shows that 68 percent of the gap is explained by discrimination whereas only 32 percent is attributed to endowment. Further, the report also finds that *discrimination accounted for only 59 percent of the total employment gap in 2004-05 which has increased significantly by 9 percent points* (Oxfam, 2022). Research has proved beyond doubt that economic independence for women is directly linked to their empowerment. In India the traditional roles (read patriarchy) are often found restraining girls and women from reaching their potentials in both the areas- of education and economic independence. Their life is entrenched in reproduction and childcare, confining them to four walls; wherein most of the time their labour remains invisible. As per 2021 ILO estimation, the labour force participation of women in India is abysmally low at 19 percent, which was 26 percent in 2010 thus showing a significant drop in LFP of women. The pandemic has

only worsened the situation compared to the national average of 51 percent for other communities. **Ruha Shadab's "Hiring Bias-Employment for Muslim women at entry-level roles"** is a revelation; despite Constitutional protection and legal provisions in place, which provide equality and disallow discrimination, the ground reality speaks of the communalisation of economic opportunities. In hiring process between men and women, the author opines, that there is no such law for religious discrimination. The study's experimental approach to identify the bias, is in line with Thorat and Attewell's (2007). The study focused on entry-level jobs and sought to look at the hiring biases between Hindu and Muslim women using equally qualified dummy profiles. The study concludes that a significant hiring bias exists against Muslim women even in instances where they are equally qualified for the job. The disparity in labour market, the author says is the *discrimination within hiring process and equal access to opportunities for Muslim women is vital to their social and financial equality in the society*. She further opines that *tackling biases in hiring process is one of the most important mechanisms by which one can level the playing field*.

Sharan Ahluwalia's article **"The missing Muslim women of Zardozi, Art and Agency among Artisans"** deals with the Muslim artisans of Zardozi craft- a heavily centralized and unorganized industry. The author takes the readers to the by-lanes of Farrukhabad and Delhi to provide a glimpse of the poverty stricken, marginalized, and vulnerable community of Muslim artisans of rich heritage. Zari zardozi is a style of embroidery that came to India from central Asia in the 12th century. An ornate and sumptuous craft, it was patronized by the affluent and courtly classes. (The Tribune, **Wednesday, 30 August 2023**). Unfortunately, the artisans behind these delicate works of Zari zardozi lead a miserable and vulnerable life. The industry is labelled as backward and inferior. A historic art-form tracing its descent from the Mughal era, zari-zardozi has for long served as a livelihood to a majority of the Muslim population. However, for the past few years, this shimmery domestic industry has been in the dark, having left in gloom thousands of workers in the city (Fatima, 2023).

Traditional crafts have suffered a set-back in the post-industrial era. Traditional weavers and spinners were made extinct through de-industrialization and then re-industrialization of the urban centres, the author quips. Liberalization has changed the market scenario; on one hand it created a demand for the handicrafts in the global market, on the other, it dwindled the domestic market for handicrafts through heavy influx of machine-made products resulting in the exclusion of the artisans from their traditional occupation as they failed miserably to compete with the market demand throwing them into penury.

Ahluwalia tries to provide an ethnographic evolution of Zardozi in India. The author tries to secure the Muslim women artisans' rights in the male dominated industry. The study was conducted in Farrukhabad (UP) and regions of Delhi. These artisans are at the mercy of the market. The work is demand based and erratic. The only labour available to earn here is Zardozi. Wages are based on piece-based compensation and commissions. The artisans struggle a lot to sustain their livelihood. Lack of market space, low wages and no recognition are some of the battles being waged by 'zari zardozi' artisans even as young entrepreneurs strive to break the barriers and make the craft a profitable pursuit (Outlook, 4th Sep. 2022). As is commonly prevalent in Muslim community mostly from lower rungs of society, women are confined to home and men work in Karkhanas. Post-puberty withdrawal of girls from school and early marriages are common. Sex segregation makes it impossible for women to learn the skills of financial dealings and market nuances. A community which already is entrenched in illiteracy, and extreme poverty, the gender divides are likely to widen. Women's contribution to the art is invisible; almost 90 percent women operate from home. Wages are low. The author feels that women are excluded both from the development and economic processes of the craft due to patriarchal power structure which regulates women's movement and takes away their agency.

They lack collective bargaining power or unionism. Lack of knowledge of various policies and programs and provisions by the State. The artisans are unaware of the schemes which are introduced to protect their art forms and cultures; and to ensure their social protection. The author strongly recommends protecting these artisans by ensuring entitlements and support in the form of benefits, training and access to markets especially in clusters of Uttar Pradesh (UP) and Delhi that have been left behind in schemes of the "One District-One Product" (ODOP) and others.

Religion-based personal laws in India have been debated from various perspectives for long; the gender dimension has only recently featured as a topic of discussion mainly by feminists and women's rights activists as has been said supra; especially the Muslim women's rights relating to divorce, inheritance, and maintenance have been the centre of attention for all and sundry. The recent political development has stirred a controversy surrounding the Muslim women's divorce through 'triple talaq'; which is declared as a criminal offence. This move of the State to treat triple talaq as a punishable offence has not gone down well with Muslims-both men and women alike. It is not only considered as an interference in their personal law but also found the move is not beneficial to the family. There is also a strong realization that the court and the judiciary lack the representation of Muslim, more so Muslim women, and hence the insecurity in accessing justice. There is more to it- the Muslim Personal Law is not codified and most of the legal

decision pronounced by the courts are based on the norms mentioned in Quran and hadith.

Indian Constitution has guaranteed equality and freedom from discrimination based on gender or religion, “for Muslim women the domain of law is liminal, and they choose between multiple legal forums to increase their access to justice”. (Rasheed & Sharma, *ibid*). There is yet another issue -a gender concern rather, that the judiciary lack sufficient number of women and that the fear that there is all possibility of women not getting their due attention with sensitivity to their grievance from male judiciary as it demands. Referring to the gender gap in judiciary, Supreme Court Judge, Justice Nazeer Ahmad observes that “*If I say Indian judiciary is immune to gender inequalities, I can't be farther away from reality. Representation of women in the judiciary is still very low*” (Jan.2023). **Maleeha Fatima** in her article “**Towards a More Inclusive Judiciary, Muslim Women's Participation and Empowerment**” discusses the changing face of judiciary with the change in political ideology in the centre. *Representation of women in judiciary is their right and a step towards undoing the centuries of marginalization that women have faced.* (CJI Justice Ramana, Sept. 2021). The author raises many pertinent questions on the make-up of judiciary and tries to address them with a gender lens and in doing so her analysis synchronizes with the other authors in the volume dealing with the issue of MPL. With the rise of Hindutva ideology and right-wing political power, she feels, the oppressed Muslim women narrative is used to produce an image of a barbaric, regressive and patriarchal Muslim society which needs external intervention (read State) to safeguard the *society being violent within itself and violent towards others*. The State's effort is to create a demonized image of a Muslim male who controls his females unjustly and hence the community is extremely patriarchal and internally flawed. As such giving an image to the world that the socioeconomic backwardness and ghettoization of Muslims in India is a result of their drawbacks regressive nature, and that State designed policies have no contribution in this. The author provides data on Muslim and non-Muslim representations at various levels of judiciary in support of her arguments. The Muslim minority has been facing discrimination by the State and therefore she feels there is an urgent need to have an effective and equitable justice system. The lackadaisical attitude of the State and its judicial machinery towards Muslim community will further marginalize the already oppressed community. It is said that

“There has never been a woman Chief Justice of India. A diversified Supreme Court will have a far-reaching impact on the public trust in the apex court which must reflect the make-up of the country. As an institution whose decisions shape and impact the everyday lives of Indians, we must do better. We must ensure, the diversity of our country finds reflection in the make-up of our court... having a more diverse judiciary is an end; a goal in itself, and worth pursuing its own sake,” (CJI Chandrachud, 2023).

‘Feminism’ has provided to the world a new definition of womanhood; given a much-needed visibility, identity, sense of equality and rights to women; provided voice and agency; and most importantly, provided feminist epistemology in the academic realm to explore and create ‘the truth’ ‘the knowledge’ from a vantage point. Feminist movements embrace concerns of sex, race, caste and religion, to name a few. It introduced to the academic world the concept of inter-sectionalism. Intersectional feminism considers the intersecting social structures of gender, race, social class, sexual orientation, religion, ability, and age, among others, as interrelated and shaping one another. *Intersectional feminists reject the idea that all women experience oppression and gender inequality in homogeneous ways. Additionally, they recognize that women rarely experience the oppression of a single factor. Using intersectional feminism moves beyond viewing gender inequality through one lens and views it as complex interactions among various structures* (Olivia Guy-Evans, 2023).

Reading of history of women’s movements in India to secure their rights and gender equality, we observe that Muslim women have played a significant role for securing women’s right to education and raising their voices against the patriarchal forces denying women their right to have agency. Many Muslim women through their writings have created awareness and are found vocal on raising their voices and are found rebellious. Initially, it was Muslim women elite who were part of the public discourses and the women from lower socioeconomic strata remain invisible. The last decade and a half brought Muslim women and their issues in public discourses, prominently. The Muslim women are found expressing and adopting a variety of non-conformist approach in religious matters. The reading provides a deep understanding of the changing contours of Muslim women’s struggles to seek an agency to secure their space within the community and outside it. The country witnessed a wide range of vibrant campaigns pioneered by Muslim association asserting women’s claims to rights as enshrines in religious texts and in Constitution; against religious conservatism and patriarchy within community. The Muslim women claim to public spaces is a common site. The ant-CAA protest will go down in the annals of history of India, a movement to which brought in fold women and men from across the communities. Breaking the shackles of subjectivity and confinement, it was the common women, not the elites alone, who raised their voices reverberated in the nook and corner creating a dynamic that left indelible mark in socio-political engagements in India. The Muslim woman of India has been, time and again, asserting her agency, she is no more invisible and voiceless.

Ghazala Jameel and Khawla Zainab’s article [Click here to enter text.](#) **“Recovering the History of Muslim Women’s Rights Movement in India”** aims at a rereading of Muslim women’s engagements and their position in the

Indian women's movements. Further, the authors present a critique of the prevailing wisdom on Muslim women's condition, status and agency. The authors opine that Muslim women's voice and agency have both suffered a systematic non-recognition, which in turn has undermined their efforts to raise their issues and attempt to bring change. Talking about various Muslim women organizations, the authors opine that their broad mandates of these organizations have been written out of the genealogies of women's movements in India and that Muslim Women have faced multi-layered betrayal from various fronts like post-colonial state, mainstream women's movement, developmental institutions, Muslim leaders and men alike. The voices in support of Muslim women are varied; some find the faults in Sharia, some in the patriarchal interpretation of verses of Qura'n; there are yet another group which blames the Muslim men in subjugating their women as part of growing up with other communities and that it is a part of acculturation and faith has nothing to do with it. There is also a significant number of women's group who insist and encourage Muslim women to read Qur'an in its true perspective and believe strongly that in essence the Qur'anic revelations are completely based on equity, equality and justice and speaks nothing short of propagating human rights, irrespective of sex, gender, race and faith and that the Muslim women must not get swayed away by the false narrative floated by the infidels and that they search for answers within the ambit of Qur'an and Ahadees. It is because Qur'an is revealed in Arabic language which a majority does not understand and its hence imperative on part of women and men to learn and seek guidance from the original sources and get empowered. There are also opinion concerning the role of socioreligious institutions, like darul qazas which are not doing Muslim women good and rendering them helpless in seeking justice in marital dispute and because of this the Muslim women are forced to take refuge under legal provisions available to them.

The authors, looking at the cases filed by the Muslim women in dar ul qazas, feel that the socioreligious institutions in fact served Muslim women in attaining their rights within and outside marriage, therefore propose to widen the discussion on women's rights beyond legal interventions. The authors have made an insightful debate to crack the false narrative spread by the communal forces about the perception of Muslim women. For instance, the authors talk of the better performance of Muslims compared to Hindus in key development indicators like IMR which uncovers the communal forces that shape the discourse, policy and perceptions of Muslim women. The authors conclude with the feminist demand for recognition of Muslim women's voice and their agency that have hitherto suffered a systematic non-recognition.

Then, there are situations which exacerbate pre-existing discrimination against women and girls, exposing them to heightened risks of violations, such as armed conflicts, post- conflict and during war & post-war-the

situations of instability. We have been witnessing a shift in situation though; earlier primarily the wars were between two countries, now there are internal conflicts within states. Women get impacted by conflicts in several ways; they have been used as tools of wars and of combat.

It is significant to recognize that hard work and interchange among women's civic movements and organizations have paved the way to the UNSCR 1325. Women's rights were first recognized as human rights at World Conference on Human Rights at Vienna in 1993, followed by the recognition of sexual violence against women as a crime of war and a crime against humanity in the year 1998 in the Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court. The four World Conferences on Women in Mexico (1975), Copenhagen (1980), Nairobi (1985) and Beijing (1995) have contributed to the drafting of WPS agenda. There are several reports citing human right violation of women and girls during conflicts raising their vulnerability, including arbitrary killing, torture, sexual violence and forced marriage. There is an exponential growth in the use of sexualized violence as a tool of war and means of combat against women (Tryggestad, 2009). Despite overwhelming evidence of rampant sexual violence in armed conflicts, it took the United Nations Security Council (UNSC) - the only body empowered to address issues of international peace and security, fifty-five years to pass its first resolution on women, peace and security (WPS). The resolution 1325 on Women, Peace and Security was adopted in the year 2000, October 31, by the Security Council, which calls for the increased participation of women and the incorporation of gender perspectives in all UN peace and security efforts (including participation of women in peace processes, gender perspectives in training and peacekeeping and gender mainstreaming in UN reporting systems). Since then, the UN Security Council has adopted a number of resolutions on women, peace and security. **Vahida Nainar's** article "**International Women, Peace and Security**" discusses the importance of the first WPS resolution 1325 and lists the subsequent resolutions on WPS that elaborates on the prevention, protection aspects of sexual violence in conflicts. The author further explores the feminist's concerns on WPS Agenda 1325. Feminists' criticism is on the ambiguous language used, and that it perpetuates gender stereotypes, reducing the roles of women in conflict to either victims or good peace builders. Feminists feel that the resolution only reproduces gendered concept of peace & war that are dominant in the patriarchal system of international security, and that link war with masculinity, and peace with femininity (Pankhurst,2003; Withworth,2004). Further, they feel it does not confront the root causes of sexual violence in conflicts that results in a violence continuum not limited to armed conflict. The article concludes that the valid critiques notwithstanding, WPS agenda of the UNSC remains important and relevant to address issues of violence against women in conflicts.

Even after more than two decades after UN adopted this landmark agenda, India is yet to develop a WPS National Action Plan (NAP) despite having borne witness to the most egregious crimes against women in disturbed or insurgency infested areas, as per a report *nearly one-sixth of India undergoes some form of armed conflict* (Khullar, 2020).

What clearly emerges is a difficult situation that Muslim women find themselves in. Fighting domestic battles against Indian cultural systems, tackling state level injustices like bans of hijab, worrying about children and husbands who are increasingly vulnerable in a divided society and seeking to undo historical setbacks, the Muslim woman has a huge battle on her hands. Within the community, there is a constant struggle against the normalisation of harassment and injustice through bogus history and convenient half truths about the scripture. Outside is an atmosphere of dread that envelops the entire community, leaving the woman doubly vulnerable. Much celebrated for their stellar role in bringing a mighty government to delay the draconian Citizenship Amendment Act, there is much pressure on the Muslim woman to take on the mantle of protest and dissent. In an atmosphere where bulldozers and mobs dispense justice, women seem to have taken on the burden of using democratic rights to speak up and push back societal and political forces that seek to redefine the Indian ethos. In this journey, the slope is steep and allies rare. However, there are many milestones that are within reach and each one, like the CAA victory, represents a major achievement. This war against hunger, deprivation, discrimination, oppression and patriarchy is going to take a while.

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